

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF KHOLAFIYAH ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF STUDENT LEARNING (CASE STUDY OF AL-ITTIHAD ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL AND MIFTAHUL HUDA AL-MUSRY ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL, CIANJUR REGENCY)

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the lack of professionalism in the management of Islamic boarding school institutions due to lack of attention to aspects of educational effectiveness and efficiency which results in low quality of learning. In general, this research aims to describe and analyze the strategic management of Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of student learning. The aim of this research is to obtain an overview of strategic environmental analysis, strategic formulation, strategic implementation, strategic control, strategic evaluation, problems and solutions to strategic management problems in Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of student learning. The research was conducted using qualitative descriptive methods, analysis based on the results of interviews, observation, documentary studies and triangulation. The research results show: 1) strategic environmental analysis of Islamic boarding schools can plan with appropriate steps through SWOT analysis. 2) the strategic formulation of the Islamic boarding school is carried out by the Islamic boarding school leadership, together with the Kyai board, and a solid team. 3) strategic implementation is carried out with a strategic plan that has been prepared. 4) strategic control establishes control principles that are based on a process that includes 8 educational standards. 5) strategic evaluation has changed weaknesses into strengths to improve the quality of Islamic boarding schools. 6) the problem of lack of human resource competency affects the management of facilities and infrastructure which is also related to Islamic boarding school policy patterns. 7) problem solutions carried out through national and international cooperation, competency development and improvements in the management of infrastructure and the substance of policy changes. Conclusions regarding the strategic management of Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of student learning is proven to be able to create quality education in accordance with 8 SNPs, and the Islamic Boarding School Law and is resilient in facing competency competition.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Kholafiyah Islamic Boarding School, Quality, Learning

INTRODUCTION

Education classification is in accordance with the provisions of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System and Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers, that every educational institution must be managed professionally according to current developments to determine a clear future direction. However, in reality, many Islamic boarding school institutions in particular, ignore this, which generally lacks professionalism in management, resulting in low quality of learning due to the effectiveness aspect of education, education is only and is still impressed in a formal form with routines without understanding the essence of education.

Kiai management and leadership are closely related to the graduates they will produce, namely producing students who are able to combine scientific theory and empirical work in the field. Islamic boarding schools are required to be ready and able to empower various potentials, resources and funding sources to become educational institutions. This view, according to Sulthon (2003: 25), in principle, Islamic boarding schools require a unique type of leader and leadership. Apart from being role models, kiai are also figures of ulama, educators, caregivers and community liaisons, therefore according to Mastuhu (2007: 255) all Islamic boarding school administrators are patterned in a centralized, hierarchical manner centered on the control and policies of the kiai. Islamic boarding school education management has two dimensions. The first is the process dimension, namely management with its functions which are process in nature, and the second is the object or material dimension, namely the components of education in Islamic boarding schools which are material in nature such as curriculum/educational materials, santri/students, teachers/clerics, teaching or educational staff, facilities and infrastructure, funds and environment.

The professionalism that is felt to still overlap is related to the management of the Khalifiyah Islamic boarding school institution, where the Islamic boarding school apart from organizing Islamic boarding school activities, also organizes formal education activities (schools), both public school channels (SO, SMP, SMU and SMK), as well as school channels. characteristic of the Islamic religion (MI, MTs, MA or MAK). This brings serious challenges, because on the one hand, Islamic boarding schools must maintain the characteristics of strong Islamic upbringing, on the other hand, Islamic boarding schools in the current era are also faced with the rapid flow of social change as a result of modernization-industrialization, so Islamic boarding schools must be able to be adaptive. and adoptive towards the two learning systems.

The success of Islamic boarding schools in responding to the current of change has become the basis for the belief of various elements of the nation, that Islamic boarding schools have a significant contribution in determining future generations. The high and low quality of the Islamic boarding school education process can be seen from how the management is controlled by the Islamic boarding school leader, the kiyai as the caretaker and also the owner of the Islamic boarding school. The strategic management of Islamic boarding schools, as stated by Dhofier (2019: 101), explains that Islamic boarding schools must grow and develop based on their own abilities, not be influenced

by momentary interests, because from the beginning, the kiyai and the community worked together to unite their strength to uphold and realize the ideals in to educate the nation's life through the establishment of Islamic boarding schools. Islamic boarding schools must reflect a source of inspiration that never dries up for lovers of science and researchers who seek to unravel anatomy from various dimensions. As an educational institution for ulama (intellectuals), it continues to carry out its mission so that the people become *tafaqquh fiddin* and motivate ulama cadres in their mission and function as *warasatul anbiya*.

The Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school is actually a development of the Salafiyah (classical) Islamic boarding school model which only teaches the Yellow Book to its students. The aim of the Kholafi Islamic boarding school is to help students gain general knowledge and technology. Therefore, at the Kholafi Islamic boarding school, they not only teach classical books, but also general teachings (formal education), so that this is the difference between the graduates of the Kholafi Islamic boarding school and the Salafis. According to Dhofier (2011: 51). views that Islamic boarding schools are divided into two categories, namely Salafi and Khalafi Islamic boarding schools. Salafi Islamic boarding schools teach classical Islamic books (the yellow book), and apply the madrasa system to facilitate the sorogan system as a teaching system. Meanwhile, Khalafi Islamic boarding schools teach using classical books and also include teaching general knowledge in them. The Islamic boarding school's struggle to gain formal legal recognition as an educational institution has led to the issuance of Minister of Religion Regulation (PMA) number 18 of 2014 concerning Mu'ilah Education Units at Islamic Boarding Schools. Until then it continued with the struggle to oversee the ratification of Law no. 18/2019 concerning Islamic Boarding Schools. So far, the government has been determined to implement centralized education politics. The government considers educational institutions that do not follow the standards in educational politics outlined by the state to be considered non-formal educational institutions whose diplomas are not recognized by the state. However, in reality, quite a few Islamic boarding schools choose not to follow the national standard curriculum as determined by the ministry of education or the ministry of religion. The Islamic boarding school's choice to stick to its salaf learning method and choose to determine its curriculum independently, hold exams and set its graduation standards independently, is a form of statement of attitude that needs to be appreciated.

The phenomenon that occurs is responded to with the paradigm that strategic management of Islamic boarding schools must be the answer to all the challenges faced above. The development of Islamic boarding schools, schools and madrasas must always carry out innovation and transformation within themselves, both in the content (material) taught and in the methods and management in order to create higher quality education as the demands of changing times. It is hoped that these changes will create a lot of progress in Islamic boarding schools, schools or madrasas. However, based on several references and also realities in the field, it seems that there are still many problems faced

by these institutions, both problems in input, process or output in achieving the goal of improving the quality of student learning.

The application of strategic management as a strategy to improve the quality of education is the root of the problem of this strategic management concept offering more education to Islamic boarding schools/schools that is better and more suitable for students. This concept emphasizes the efforts of Islamic boarding schools to determine what they want to achieve and how they must achieve useful results within the scope of education so that the institution understands competitive forces and systematically develops sustainable and consistent competitive advantages. Education should continue to be developed in accordance with the changes and challenges of the times. Therefore, the quality of education as one of the pillars of human resource development is very important for the development of the country, it could even be said that the future of the nation lies in quality education today. Quality education can only be achieved if there are high quality educational institutions, so improving the quality of education is strategic issues in creating quality education. Strategic management is an effective management tool and is definitely involved in educational management, to explain methods and approaches in achieving educational goals, evaluate strategic alternatives using certain criteria and select alternatives or groups that can become educational strategies.

Responding to the challenges of the times, and being responsible for improving the social and cultural conditions of Indonesia which have been destroyed by the changing times, clashing waves of modernization, globalization, capitalism and other currents. It is social change that cannot be rejected that Islamic boarding schools must become a bull and a catalyst for economic growth and political movement in society (ethical). Islamic boarding schools have a responsibility to improve the socio-cultural conditions in Indonesia which have been destroyed as a result of this. So strengthening religious sciences is a very fundamental foundation as a basis for pursuing advances in science and other technologies.

METHOD

Based on the problem focus, objectives and characteristics, the approach used in this research is a qualitative approach with a case study method. The researcher chose to use a qualitative research method with a case study approach. The two main objectives of using the methods used by researchers are none other than, firstly, to describe and explore and secondly to describe and explain. This research seeks to describe and analyze the real conditions of two Islamic boarding schools regarding the stages of strategic management implementation which include: internal and external environmental analysis, strategic planning of Islamic boarding schools, strategic implementation of Islamic boarding schools, strategic evaluation of Islamic boarding schools, strategic problems of Islamic boarding schools and solutions in overcoming problems. Islamic boarding school strategy in improving the quality of student learning. Researchers want to investigate and understand an event or problem that has occurred by collecting various

kinds of information which is then processed to obtain a solution so that the problem uncovered can be resolved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Strategic environmental analysis

Although the two Islamic boarding schools that are the subject of research are more familiar with the term school-based management (SBM) rather than using the term strategic management, in general both Islamic boarding schools have carried out management or management of Islamic boarding schools/schools in accordance with the basic elements of the strategic management process proposed by Wheelen and Hunger (2003:11), namely having carried out environmental analysis (environmental scanning), strategic formulation (strategy formulation), strategic implementation (strategy implementation), as well as monitoring and assessment (evaluation and control). Implementing good strategic management will improve school performance so that school quality will be realized. In two Kholafiyah Islamic boarding schools in improving the quality of learning without any advantages, strengths or weaknesses, these advantages or strengths become an advantage for Islamic boarding schools in improving the quality of learning. The SWOT analysis will look at the advantages of the vision and mission, facilities and human resources that support the two Islamic boarding schools. So it can minimize the impact of competition. The current threat to Islamic boarding schools is competition in the business world and the world of work. By looking at the recognition of Islamic boarding school graduates, it becomes a threat when the quality of their learning is not improved according to the standards set by the government. Environmental studies (analysis) at the Al-Ittihad Islamic Boarding School and at Al-Musri Cianjur were carried out as a basis for preparing the Medium Term Work Plan (RKJM) and Long Term Work Plan (RKJP). Identify and then review the level of performance that has been achieved as material for preparing future work plans. In general, strategic management principles in the internal and external analysis steps have been implemented and provide superiority to work programs, because the work plans prepared have been adjusted to developments occurring in the environment around the Islamic boarding school/school. Environmental influences are managed so as to maximize improvements in school performance. The purpose of environmental analysis is to recognize the organization's internal strengths and weaknesses and understand the organization's external opportunities and challenges, so that the organization can inspire change efforts that must be carried out in the future. A similar thing was stated by Akdon (2006: 107) that "environmental analysis is useful for detecting important changes and events, especially those related to the social, political, economic, technological and scientific advances; identify challenges, opportunities or changes caused by important events to the organization". Environmental analysis provides information regarding future orientation to each level of leadership and staff, giving signs to all levels about what must be done about the organization.

b. Strategic formulation

The findings obtained from the results of interviews, observations and documentation carried out by researchers, Al-itihad Islamic boarding school has a document establishing a Vision and Mission which are shared ideals in achieving organizational goals as a reference for Islamic boarding school residents in order to achieve the results expected by the community. Strategic to achieve the goals that have been formulated in the RKT/RKAS and RKJM based on internal and external environmental analysis. As a priority in term, short, medium term and urgent work programs. Strategic formulation is implemented effectively. Establish policies in developing activities to improve the quality of Islamic boarding schools. Meanwhile, the Al-Musri Islamic boarding school shows that: The formulation of the vision, mission, goals and strategies of the Islamic boarding school is carried out objectively, effectively and efficiently. Developing an integrated education system, integrating learning programs through the development of science and technology and Imtaq, informing the results to the community and school committees in order to improve the quality of Islamic boarding schools. Strategic formulation is carried out by developing strategic matters such as human resource development, infrastructure, effective learning. Establish policies within Islamic boarding school leadership in transforming policies for all managers in their respective fields to develop activities to improve the quality of Islamic boarding school education. Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of learning is in accordance with management theory, carried out by formulating a vision, mission, goals, learning quality targets, strategies and policies. The long-term plans included in the program are between three and five years. The application of indicators in the strategic formulation of the two Islamic boarding schools has fulfilled several elements, including time, clarity and improvement of program design, both long and short term. The strategic formulation of Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of student learning in both Islamic boarding schools is carried out through long-term and short-term program planning. The long-term and short-term planning is formulated in programs that contain the curriculum, regarding achievement standards that must be implemented in curriculum, and management standards.

c. Strategic implementation

Based on strategic management theory from Hunger & Wheelen (2013: 17) explains that "strategic implementation is a process in which top management, in this case the principal, improves strategies and policies in action through the development of programs, budgets and procedures". The advantages of strategic planning will not be meaningful if it is not implemented according to the provisions. Strategic implementation in school management is an effort to translate planning into action, namely the implementation of school programs. The situation at the research location can be described as showing that strategic goals have guided the direction of the organization/company in achieving long-term goals. Helping organizations/companies adapt when competitors emerge. Preparation of programs carried out by Islamic boarding school leaders to improve the quality of Islamic boarding schools related to the educational goals of Islamic boarding

schools to produce ulama cadres by evaluating the quality improvement of Islamic boarding schools. Revising Document I, Document II and Document III, Supervision Program, Meeting Agenda, Preparation of Annual Work Program, Long Term Work Program, Islamic Boarding School Rules of Conduct, KBM SK, Distribution of Additional Duties, Picket Schedule, Minutes, Attendance List. Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of learning, orientation refers to goals, program preparation. preparation of the budget, preparation of procedures have been carried out well. The implementation is by implementing programs from the 8 National Education Standards and establishing educational quality assurance standards in accordance with the standards set by the government which are then realized in the two Islamic boarding schools in accordance with the Islamic boarding school's characteristics.

d. Strategic control

Control is the final part before the evaluation process of an activity process to make an organization achieve its goals. According to Siswanto (2005: 139-140), strategic management control is a systematic effort to obtain performance standards with planning targets, design an information feedback system, compare actual performance with predetermined standards, determine whether there are deviations and measure the significance of these deviations, and take necessary corrective action to ensure that all current company resources are used as much as possible more effectively and efficiently to achieve company goals. Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school education in improving the quality of student learning at both Islamic boarding schools is carried out by ustadz/teachers, Islamic boarding school leaders (kiyai), the Masayaih Council and the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia in accordance with the Islamic boarding school law. establish control principles in the 8 SNP process, from these results continuous improvements are made if there are deviations. Therefore, the management of the Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school will ensure that the process refers to analyzing problem solving and finding solutions.

e. Strategic evaluation

Strategic evaluation is the final stage of strategic management. Even though it is the last step, this step is as important as strategy formulation. All of this is due to the expertise or ability to coordinate various tasks that must be carried out by various parties, both from the supervisory side and the work units of each organization through work control. Strategic evaluation of the leadership at the two Islamic boarding schools has turned weaknesses into strengths to improve the quality of Islamic boarding schools. The external environment participates in evaluating the implementation of strategic management by Islamic boarding school leaders. Islamic boarding schools will be of high quality if all Islamic boarding school education policies and programs receive support from all components. Therefore, all components that support efforts to achieve the goals of education providers can be empowered, all components through community participation in improving the quality of educational services in Islamic boarding schools through the results of the evaluation process.

f. Problems encountered

Problems that often arise in an organization as well as in Islamic boarding schools are none other than HR competency issues. HR management has a special place in the implementation of Islamic boarding schools. But still, Islamic boarding schools often experience problems that are not easy, for example the condition of competence and professionalism of the HR bureaucracy which is carried out without careful planning and concepts. The dilemma faced by educational institutions is that the aim of education should be to improve the quality of human resources. One effort to improve this is through learning in schools, efforts to improve the quality of educational resources, teachers are part of what must be promoted and continue to be developed. The need for potential teacher resources grows and develops to be able to carry out their duties effectively and professionally. Apart from that, the impact of rapid change is also quite encouraging for teachers to learn to adapt to developments in information science and technology as well as societal mobility. However, on the other hand, the responsibility for human resource development and teacher professionalism is a heavy burden that must be borne by educational institutions, not to mention this which will later be related to the budget, facilities and infrastructure as well as the policies of an institution itself. findings at the research location, imply that the problem of developing human resources in Islamic boarding schools is due to the absence of organizational training in Islamic boarding schools, Islamic boarding school administrators do not know how to manage a professional Islamic boarding school system, causing the competency of Islamic boarding school administrators to not develop, there are deficiencies that must be met. maximized from the direction and support of Islamic boarding school foundation administrators in order to provide training or develop HR competencies to improve skills, improve technical competencies, increase knowledge about how to organize well. Facilities and infrastructure are quite mediocre, Islamic boarding school funds to support operations are still weak, and inadequate provision for procurement and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure is a problem for preparing budgets for improving the quality of Islamic boarding schools. This influences the policies taken, because they adapt to the realities on the ground.

g. Problem solution

Efforts are made to achieve this, namely by working hard and working sincerely, full of commitment, discipline, and always making improvements through criticism and suggestions by involving all residents, both Islamic boarding school residents and parents of students, and community members in the Islamic boarding school environment to supports the program to improve 8 national standards as a reference for school quality. In addition, managing the school through careful planning is implemented, which is then monitored and assessed for future improvements. The problem solutions taken by the two Islamic boarding schools have had an impact on improving the quality of student learning, developing human resources, Islamic boarding school leaders and other educational staff, increasing conducive teaching and learning process activities. An important element in the management of facilities and infrastructure that must be

adequate to support learning is carried out regularly so that it is in accordance with the goals expected by the institution. The substance of the change in Islamic boarding school policy from schools specializing in religious studies to general schools with Islamic religious characteristics is in order to direct, guide, develop and produce qualified Islamic boarding school educational output, capable of developing a view of life (cognitive), attitude to life (affective) and life skills (motor) from an Islamic perspective, so as to create perfect Indonesian humans.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research findings, interpretation and discussion, the researcher can conclude that in general the strategic management of education at the Kholafiyah Islamic boarding school in improving the quality of student learning in the two Islamic boarding schools has carried out strategic management activities to improve the quality of learning well. This is proven by the existence of strategic management activities that focus on improving the quality of learning, which is closely related to organizational performance, human resources, especially ustadz/teachers who are part of the education system which occupies a strategic position in the management and development of learning. Organizational management refers to the management functions themselves, running in a planned, systematic, continuous manner in accordance with learning quality standards. The results of this research provide recommendations to:

- a. For the government, it is necessary to set a standard for improving the quality of learning in Islamic boarding schools. Providing strengthening of Islamic boarding school education policies that are more holistic in nature, as well as ensuring financial support for improving the quality of Islamic boarding school learning, whether sourced from the APBN or government APBD.
- b. For other Islamic boarding schools, it can be used as a practical reference guide for improving and enhancing services, learning, teachers, facilities and infrastructure, management, academic climate and learning processes in order to improve services, graduates and learning quality.
- c. For PT IAI, the other parties need to have a strong commitment to collaborate and synergize together in the education quality assurance process, because if one of the parties is less than optimal or lacks commitment in carrying out education quality assurance, it will be difficult to realize the objectives 8 SNP.
- d. For the community, maximizing the role of parents, school committees, alumni networks, universities and collaboration with other institutions to develop Islamic boarding school/school activity programs that lead to quality learning.
- e. For future researchers, it can be used as input, sources of information and further reference materials to further develop better strategic management programs.

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